

GENERAL LECTURE 1

Composites in Engineering

A. Kelly

University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey GU2 5XH, England

ABSTRACT

A composite material can be defined as a heterogeneous mixture of two or more homogeneous phases which have been bonded together.

The fibrous composite is a special case designed to utilise the high strength and stiffness of many modern fibres. The mechanical properties of such a composite are compared with those of some other composites used in engineering such as cemented carbide cutting tools, pneumatic tyres and cellular materials such as cork.

The physical properties can be taken to be of two types (a) those in which the properties are independent of the size of the individual pieces of the two components and (b) those in which the control of the dimensions of one of the phases is the essential reason for making the composite.

Elastic mechanical properties fall under the designation (a); all other mechanical properties such as tensile strength, fatigue or creep fall under the designation (b).

For composites containing aligned fibres, it is necessary to start with a simple problem such as the ultimate tensile strength and to attempt to derive laws of additivity. Examples where this has been possible will be given. Attempts have been made to deduce colligative rules for composites creeping in parallel. These will be reviewed. In fatigue the problem is so ill-defined that it is only really possible to identify now some cases of the feature controlling fracture.

1. INTRODUCTION

A composite material can be defined as a heterogeneous mixture of two or more homogeneous phases which have been bonded together. Provided the individual pieces of the two phases are not easily seen with the naked eye, then the composite resulting can itself be regarded as a homogeneous material. Most natural materials such as wood are composites as well as a motor car tyre, glass reinforced plastics, the cemented carbides used as cutting tools, or paper - a composite consisting of cellulose fibres, sometimes with a filler, often clay. Paper is essentially a mat of fibres with interfibre bonding being provided by

hydrogen bonds where the fibres touch one another.

The combination is usually spoken of as a composite material provided that it has its own distinctive properties, such as being tougher than either of the two materials used alone or for instance having a negative thermal expansion coefficient or having some other property not clearly shown by either of the two component materials.

Composite materials can be thought of, in principle, which produce hitherto unobtainable properties in a single material; for instance by combining a piezoelectric material with another which shows magnetostriction one could produce a material showing a magneto electric effect ie an applied magnetic field would induce an electric dipole moment. Alternatively one could produce a material in which an applied magnetic field produced optical birefringence by coupling a material which shows strain induced birefringence with another showing magnetostriction. Nowadays the term "composite" often means specifically the combination of very strong and stiff fibres with a weak matrix designed to hold the fibres together. This type of composite exhibits the extreme strength of the fibres and, due to the presence of the weaker matrix, shows much greater toughness than would otherwise be obtainable.

The term "composite" originally arose when two or more materials were combined in order to rectify some shortcoming of a particularly useful component. Its first use in engineering, so far as I am aware, was in the early "Clipper" sailing ships which consisted of wood planking on iron frames, the wood covered with plates of copper in order to counter the attack of marine organisms on the wood.

In many cases, the dimensions of one of the phases of a composite material are small, say between 10nm and a few microns, and under these conditions that particular phase has physical properties rather different from that of the same material in the bulk form. Striking examples are the strengths of fibres of glass or graphite, of boron, or of pure silica and many whisker crystals. In order to utilise the strength of such strong materials, they must be stuck together in some form - a rope is possible, for instance, for strong fibres of hemp or flax and indeed carbon fibres are often twisted into tows as is glass. However, for proper utilisation, one looks for a matrix in which to embed such strong fibres in order to provide a strong and stiff solid. When that is done, the properties of the matrix are usually chosen so as to provide some other property lacking in the inherent properties of the fibres themselves; for instance, great toughness. The resulting combination is then designed so as to achieve high strength and stiffness (due to the fibres) and resistance to crack propagation (due to the interaction between fibres and matrix).

Other examples are magnetic materials in which the particle size of the ferro magnetic is less than the normal domain size, so that the individual particles are single domains and are saturated magnetically. Such domains put together with a minimum of binder provide a permanent magnet of very high coercive force.

Dental cements of the newer kind consist of particles of an alumino-fluoro-silicate glass stuck together with polyacrylic acid and materials to replace ceramics, at least for low temperature use, now consist of grains of sand bound in polymethylmethacrylate.

Once the efficacy of the principle of combining two or more materials in order to obtain new properties is realised, then the choice of the components introduces a new concept, namely that of materials engineering, or designing the new material by putting together or compositing two or more known materials.

2. PNEUMATIC TYRES

A pneumatic tyre is an example of a composite structure in the form of a series of parallel cords embedded in rubber. The rubber itself contains a filler - carbon black, as well as cheaper fillers, which are added in order to increase

the abrasion resistance, tear strength and modulus of the rubber. In addition rubbers used in tyres for motor cars contain considerable quantities of oil in order to increase hysteresis and to enhance the "grip" on the road.

Because it is a structure of particular geometric form being made by compression moulding at a temperature of about 140°C - 200°C (the vulcanization temperature) of the rubber around the reinforcing cord, the properties of the composite material which forms the rubber are not usually considered but only those of the initial cord and of the (uncompounded) rubber. The structure of the tyre defines the type, number, location and dimensions of the various components used in the composite. The reinforcing material in a tyre has the same function as the glass in a glass reinforced plastic and the reinforcing rods embedded in concrete. The cords give the tyre its strength, dimensional stability, bruise resistance - rubber has poor fatigue resistance if continuously flexed, and the reinforcing cord prevents this.

Today there are two basic types of automobile tyre; cross-ply which contains multiple plies (or layers) of parallel cords extending in alternate layers at opposing acute angles, and radial ply in which there are two distinct types of plies - those which go radially round the tyre to form the carcass and layers arranged as in the cross ply tyre beneath the tread. The former construction is analogous to that of angle ply laminated fibre composites; the latter is designed to uncouple the load bearing members, which are the radial carcass plies, from the tread reinforcing members.

A variety of materials are used or have been used as the cord materials in tyres ranging from rayon, via synthetic textiles, polyethylene terephthalate and the polyaromatic amides, to steel wires. The difference in elastic modulus between cord and matrix is very large - up to four orders of magnitude in the case of steel and so the integrity of the bonding at the interface under both static and dynamic conditions is extremely important. Theories of the behaviour of reinforced rubber and of reinforced resins or metals have rarely made contact until recently - see for example Murthy and Bhowick (1).

3. STRESS-STRAIN CURVE OF PAPER

Paper is essentially a mat of fibres, sometimes containing small amounts of a filler - chalk or clay - and a small amount of glue. Better quality papers contain no filler. It is a mat of fibres without a matrix, bonding being provided by hydrogen bonds where the fibres touch. Paper made from wood or other natural fibres differs from paper-like substances made from synthetic fibres in being much stiffer and in its ability to sustain a sharp fold.

The stress strain curve of paper both in the elastic and plastic regime is now quite well understood - an excellent summary is provided in (2), see also (3). Page and Coworkers start from an equation derived first by Cox for the in plane elastic modulus of paper E_p .

$$E_p = \frac{1}{3} E_f \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{w}{l} \right) \frac{E_f}{2G_f} \tanh \left[\alpha \left(\frac{l}{w} \right) \sqrt{\frac{2G_f}{E_f}} \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

E_f , G_f , w , l , are the Young modulus, shear modulus, mean width and mean length of the fibres. α is called the relative bonded area and is measured by optical scattering in reflection. The fibre lengths in paper are around 1mm on average and values of E_f directly measured on straight fibres about 80 GN/m^2 (4) which compares with calculated values from assumed atomic force constants for cellulose - see eq (5) - of 56 GN/m^2 . For long fibres the factor of $\frac{1}{3}$ has been directly verified and variations in the quantity α may be brought about without altering E_f eg by increasing the wet pressing pressure and the length dependence of equation (1) has been checked.

Paper, and the fibres of which it is composed, show a stress strain curve of

of the type illustrated in Fig 1, showing elastic behaviour to a strain of about 0.5% and hysteresis on subsequent unloading with a pronounced permanent set or the ability to demonstrate a form of plasticity. This plasticity shows a strong resemblance to that shown by cements reinforced by synthetic fibres such as polypropylene. The plastic extensions possible in the individual fibres, such as that shown in Fig 2 are much greater than the corresponding extensions for paper but nonetheless a paper will show extensions of some 2-3%.

The nature of the plastic extension has been perplexing and it has been explained as due to disruption of interfibre bonds or else as due to irreversible intrafibre flow. That the latter explanation appears to be the most persuasive one emerges from the following observations of which a striking one is the observation of stress strain curves for the component fibres of the type shown in Fig 2. These fibres are not straight but have been compressed in the wet state in order to produce microkinks prior to their extension. In addition altering interfibre bonding while affecting the breaking strength has no effect on the stress strain curve and the same is true of change in bonded area. The work on single fibres illustrates that flow occurs within them and it has also been shown that in a paper the individual fibres are not straight and during extension of the paper the small kinks are straightened out in a plastic manner showing all the features of permanent set, delayed elastic recovery, creep and stress relaxation. Some bond breakage does occur and it is this which leads to a real decrease in elastic modulus after straining.

4. THE FOAM COMPOSITE - CORK

Another composite, and one containing voids (usually filled with air) as one of the constituents, is the foam consisting of a network of rigid walls. A useful review of synthetic rigid foams is given by Nicholls (6). Inorganic foams are coming on to the market and the important technological properties of these and of conventional synthetic organic foams are stiffness, strength, thermal conductivity and damping characteristics. All foams are used for some form of insulation, be it heat or sound. Some recent work has been concerned with the strength (7,8) elastic moduli (9) and a comprehensive treatment (10,11) of both based upon an interest in cork has appeared. Cork is the prime natural cellular material occurring (at least as a thin layer) in all trees. It is of interest to biologists that the word "cell" was first coined by Hooke from a study of cork. Gibson et al (10) model cork as a two-dimensional foam containing hexagonal cells which at their simplest are closed hexagonal prisms. The elastic anisotropy of this foam-like structure can be identified in terms of bending and stretching of the cell walls and the strength, or at least the initial collapse load of the structure, in terms of the buckling of the cell walls. Cork differs from most artificial foams in that the cell walls are about $1\mu\text{m}$ thick and the value of ℓ in the inset in Table 1 is usually about $20\mu\text{m}$. A commercial polystyrene or polyurethane foam has a wall thickness of $10\text{-}20\mu\text{m}$ and ℓ/t between 8 and 20; in the inorganic foam appearing on the market (ℓ/t) is again between 10 and 20 and t also $12\text{-}15\mu\text{m}$.

For a hexagonal foam of infinite extent in one direction consisting of a honeycomb-like array of hexagons Gibson et al - see Table 1 - have calculated the elastic moduli and the compressive elastic (and plastic) collapse loads in terms of the dimension of the structure and the properties of the material of the cell wall, designated by subscript s, E = Young's modulus, G = shear modulus, ν = Poisson's ratio and ρ = density. There are four independent elastic constants in the plane of the diagram which can be written as two Young's moduli, a Poisson ratio and a shear modulus (as for a single lamella in conventional composite theory). At strains of $\sim 10\%$ foams cease to be linearly elastic; cell walls buckle and large deformations occur at almost constant load. If the material of the cell walls is capable of undergoing plastic deformation then a plastic collapse stress may be defined at the point when the bending moment in a beam reaches the fully plastic moment.

The results shown in Table 1 indicate, rather surprisingly to my mind, that not only the elastic modulus but also the elastic and plastic collapse stresses can be written in terms of the dimensionless variable (E/ρ_s) and (t/ℓ) (or (h/ℓ) in

in the non-regular case) which means that the mechanical properties are independent of the absolute dimensions of the cell walls. This is not true of the properties governing heat flow through a cellular structure, where convection and radiation effects can depend on cell size. Table 2 shows that Gibson et al obtain quite good agreement for the in-plane moduli and collapse stresses of cork in terms of their theory with the exception of the calculated value of Poisson ratio. However they can explain, on their model of the structure, the important value of zero for the Poisson ratio connecting an imposed in-plane deformation and the resulting deformation parallel to the hexagonal axis.

5. THE ULTIMATE PARTICULATE COMPOSITE (WC-Co)

An example, where the properties of both phases are only realised if each is in small pieces is in tungsten carbide grains used in a cutting tool. In fact in this composite neither phase has properties in the composite similar to those observed when the components are tested separately. When tungsten carbide, or other hard carbide, grains are only of a few microns in size, they do not easily crack. Small pieces of a few microns in linear dimension must be held together in some way, and the matrix chosen to bind them is cobalt, because it both dissolves and wets tungsten carbide. Compacts are made by liquid phase sintering at a temperature of 1350^o-1550^oC, ie above the solidus temperature of cobalt saturated with tungsten carbide, so containing 2-10% W. A very uniform microstructure is produced of theoretical density and if it is not the properties show marked deterioration - even larger carbide grains than normal can cause a decrease in strength. The volume fractions of importance are greater than 80% of WC and so these materials have provided confirmation of the calculation of elastic moduli to very large volume fractions (Hashin and Shtrikman, (11)).

In the composite the properties of both phases are modified, the tungsten carbide undergoes plastic deformation and the yield stress of the cobalt is greatly increased. Many studies eg Lee and Gurland (12), Murray (13) show conclusively that the hardness of the material, as does that of each of the constituents, depends on the square root of a structural dimension. The hardness of the carbide varies inversely as the square root of the mean particle size and that of the cobalt inversely as the square root of the mean free path in the cobalt. For the composite the hardness varies as the volume fraction of carbide multiplied by the contiguity (which is a measure of the fraction of WC grains which are in contact with one another and not with the cobalt). In fact the hardness varies as

$$H_c = CV H_c + (1 - CV) H_m \quad (2)$$

where both H_c and H_m must be calculated for the particular particle size and mean free path respectively and C is the contiguity. V is the volume fraction of WC.

On the other hand the square of the critical stress intensity, or the work of fracture, each depends accurately upon the mean free path in the cobalt. The properties are markedly affected by whether carbide particles are in contact or not and there is difficulty in establishing whether or not this occurs at large volume fraction.

The values of the hardness of cobalt and of the value of K_{IC} at large volume fractions of tungsten carbide indicate extreme resistance to plastic flow. Values of the yield stress of about 6 GN/m² are deduced by Murray (13) and of the hardness of about 8 GN/m². There are an order of magnitude greater than the values for this material measured outside the composite and Murray calculates that the material fails when the cobalt reaches its ideal (theoretical) strength. If this is so, this particular composite has reached the ultimate in its mechanical properties.

6. LONGITUDINAL TENSILE FAILURE OF ALIGNED FIBROUS COMPOSITES

All theories of failure in tension depend upon the identification of a point

of instability in the load extension curve either because of the presence of a crack or because of structural failure during extension of some component of the composite. In the latter case a rough approximation to the strength in tension is obtained from a "law of mixtures" which identifies the strength as equal to the normally observed breaking strength of each component multiplied by its respective volume fraction.

There are two cases in which this should be true for bundles of fibres. The first is the well known metal case (Mileiko, 14; Garmong and Thompson, 15) and the second is for bundles of brittle fibres consisting of fibres of more than one type.

Consider a bundle of two sets of fibres designated 1 and 2 loaded in parallel from their ends each consisting of a large number of fibres N of average area A . Then if σ is the stress and F the load on the hybrid bundle, the condition for tensile stability is

$$dF = A_1 N_1 d\sigma_1 + \sigma_1 d(A_1 N_1) + A_2 N_2 d\sigma_2 + \sigma_2 d(A_2 N_2) \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

Obviously the product AN represents the total cross sectional area of a component. In the case of a ductile component, undergoing work hardening, the stress increases because of a decrease in cross sectional area demanded by the constancy of volume during plastic extension. In this case, if σ is the strain on the composite and hence the same in both components, we have, dividing by $(A_1 N_1 + A_2 N_2)$

$$V_1 \left(\frac{d\sigma_1}{d\epsilon} - \sigma_1 \right) + V_2 \left(\frac{d\sigma_2}{d\epsilon} - \sigma_2 \right) \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

as the condition of stability, because, in this case,

$$d\epsilon = \frac{-d(A_1 N_1)}{A_1 N_1} = \frac{-d(A_2 N_2)}{A_2 N_2} \quad (5)$$

Since in (4) the quantity in brackets must be positive for stability of each component strained separately, it follows that, if each component strained separately has the same ultimate tensile strain, then the ultimate tensile strain of the composite will occur at this strain and the law of mixtures will be rigorously true. This of course is unlikely. By using particular expressions for the plastic load extension curve, Mileiko and Garmong (14, 15) separately show that the ultimate tensile strain of the composite must lie between those of the two components and they give bounds for the uts of which the law of mixtures is an upper limit. However, there is no need to invoke particular forms for the variation of stress with strain in order to show that the law of mixtures is an upper limit for the strength or that the ultimate tensile strain lies between that of the two components. Both follow from (4) as we show below.

If we apply equation (1) to two brittle components both assumed elastic to failure, the areas A_1, A_2 can be treated as constants and during tensile straining of the bundle the values N_1 and N_2 decrease as a function of strain. In this case $d\sigma/d\epsilon =$ Youngs modulus and (σ/E) is the strain in the fibres, so, writing

$n_1 = \frac{N_1}{N_{O1}}$ and $n_2 = \frac{N_2}{N_{O2}}$, where N_{O1} and N_{O2} are the initial number of fibres of each type in the population, we have

$$V_1 E_1 \left(n_1 + \epsilon \frac{dn_1}{d\epsilon} \right) + V_2 E_2 \left(n_2 + \epsilon \frac{dn_2}{d\epsilon} \right) \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

as the condition for tensile stability. The uts of the hybrid bundle is obtained by solving for ϵ using the equals sign in (4) so as to obtain a value of ϵ_{ult} and substituting this for ϵ in the equation

$$F_{ult} = V_1 E_1 n_1 \epsilon + V_2 E_2 n_2 \epsilon \quad (7)$$

Without introducing expressions for $n(\epsilon)$ and $dn/d\epsilon$, certain consequences follow immediately from (6) and (7). $n(\epsilon)$ is a monotonically decreasing function of ϵ so $(\frac{dn}{d\epsilon})$ is always negative. Since the product VE is necessarily positive it follows that the tensile strain of the hybrid bundle always lies between that of the two components. To see this, suppose that fibres of type 1 have the smaller value of ϵ_{ult} - the value of the strain at which a bundle of these fibres tested separately reaches its uts - then when the strain of the hybrid ϵ_h reaches ϵ_{ult1} the first term in question (6) equals zero but the second term is still positive so a greater strain must be reached before equation (6) is satisfied. Also since the first term must be negative at the strain at which ϵ_{ult2} is reached, then ϵ_h must be less than ϵ_{ult2} .

An analogous argument may be applied to equation (4) for the ductile case.

We also see from (7) that the largest value of the uts of the hybrid is obtained if both populations of fibres possess the same value of the ultimate tensile strain when tested as separate bundles. This is because $V_1 E_1$ and $V_2 E_2$ are positive constants and the fact that for a single fibre population the uts occurs when the product $n\epsilon$ is a maximum. Clearly the largest value of (7) occurs when the product $n\epsilon$ has its maximum value for both types of fibres at the same strain; which will be the ultimate strain of the hybrid in this case.

Bundle theory of this simple type cannot be used immediately for a composite consisting of brittle fibres in a resin matrix because of two factors. These are (a) because of the lack of definition of the length of fibres in the bundle and (b) because of stress concentrations placed on neighbouring fibres when a fibre breaks. The mathematics of methods to assess (b) and the criteria for failure are very complicated eg Harlow and Phoenix (16) - although a simple approximate way of considering these has been given by Batdorf and Ghaffarian (17). However, even if the problem of local stress concentration is satisfactorily solved, the length of bundle to be considered still remains as an undefined quantity chosen to fit experiment.

In the case of both components deforming plastically the simple model of an unstable bundle of filaments must be modified because the plastic properties of the weaker phase become modified by the presence of the more rigid material which is usually the fibre. This is apparent from the experiments of Kelly and Lilholt (18) and can be explained in terms of the theory of plastic deformation of a crystal containing non-defining inclusions - the so-called Perfect Memory Solid - taking into account the reduction in interfibre spacing due to dislocations being forced to stand off from the particles (Brown and Clarke, 19).

7. CREEP

If fibres and matrix creep longitudinally in parallel the stress σ_c necessary to cause a given creep rate is given simply by adding the stress necessary in each component in order to obtain,

$$\sigma_c = V_1 \sigma_1(\dot{\epsilon}) + V_2 \sigma_2(\dot{\epsilon}) \quad (8)$$

The conditions of stability now become more complex because they depend on both strain rate and on strain. If strain rate only is considered, the deformation is unstable should stress depend on strain rate to a power less than one, ie if n in the expression

$$\sigma = \frac{\dot{\epsilon}^{1/n}}{B} \quad (9)$$

is greater than one. This is almost always the case. However long ranges of strain under stable conditions are found in creeping composites and even fracture of one of the components does not lead to immediate instability.

When the matrix creeps but the fibres remain elastic the initial strain will be $\epsilon_0 = \sigma_c / (E_1 V_1 + E_2 V_2)$ and creep must die out at a strain

$$\epsilon_\infty = \frac{\sigma_c}{E_1 V_1} \quad (10)$$

where subscript 2 denotes the matrix and subscript 1 the fibre and E denotes Young's modulus.

If creep occurs at constant stress the stress in the matrix is given by

$$\sigma_2 = -\dot{\epsilon} \frac{E_1 V_1}{V_2} \quad (11)$$

So, if it is assumed (McLean, 20) that the rate of creep of the matrix is given by an empirical rule such as

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{\dot{\epsilon}_2}{E_2} + B_2 \sigma_2^{n_2} \quad (12)$$

then, during transient creep of the composite, we have

$$\dot{\epsilon} = B_2 \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{V_2} \right)^{n_2} \left\{ 1 + \frac{E_1 V_1}{E_2 V_2} \right\}^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon E_1 V_1}{\sigma_c} \right)^{n_2}$$

or

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \alpha \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon E_1 V_1}{\sigma_c} \right)^{n_2} = \alpha \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_\infty} \right)^{n_2} \quad (13)$$

where $\alpha = B_2 \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{V_2} \right)^{n_2} \left\{ 1 + \frac{E_1 V_1}{E_2 V_2} \right\}^{-1}$

and ϵ_∞ is the final total strain; thus showing that the rate of straining decreases with increase of strain, the more rapidly with increase in strain, the larger the value of n_2 . The strain varies between the values ϵ_0 and ϵ_∞ according to the relation

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_\infty - (\epsilon_\infty - \epsilon_0) \left[1 + \left\{ 1 - \frac{\epsilon_0}{\epsilon} \right\}^{n_2-1} \frac{\alpha t (n-1)}{\epsilon_\infty} \right]^{-\frac{1}{n_2-1}} \quad (14)$$

There is no true steady state, so if the fibres do not show static fatigue the important design parameter is the time to reach a given strain. This is also larger for larger values of n_2 , and the rate of straining decreases asymptotically to zero as the strain in the composite approaches ϵ_∞ given by (10).

The case when both matrix and fibres creep has been considered by McDanel et al (21) and by Street (22). If both components obey a power law of the type of (7) then the stress on the composite required to produce a given creep rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ is

$$\sigma_c = \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{B_1} \right)^{1/n_1} V_1 + \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{B_2} \right)^{1/n_2} V_2 \quad (15)$$

Then the composite does not possess a unique stress sensitivity n_c even though both fibres and matrix do. This is shown in Figs 3 and 4, where composite creep

curves have been calculated from the given matrix and fibre curves for two values of V_f (0.1 and 0.5). The exponent n_c depends on both volume fraction and on the strain - see Fig 4. Any change in either fibre or matrix stress sensitivity at high stresses would produce a similar change in the composite stress exponent. The effect of neglecting the matrix in a creep calculation of this sort is shown in Fig 3 by the dotted line $\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f$ for $V_f (= V_1)$ equal to both 0.1 and 0.5.

In determining reliable activation energies for creep great care must be taken to determine whether all or only part of the applied stress is available to do work during the activation process.

Creep behaviour of microstructurally complex alloys are characterised by anomalously large values of the stress exponent n and of the activation energy Q , if analysed in terms of the usual power law expression. To remove this anomaly an expression of the form

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A(\sigma - \sigma_o)^n \exp - Q/RT \quad (16)$$

should be used (McLean, 20). For appropriate values of σ_o the creep data of most materials yield values of n of about 4 with Q approximately equal to the activation energy for self diffusion in the dislocation creep regime.

σ_o is called the friction stress by advocates of recovery controlled creep, and is called the back stress by advocates of activated slip models of creep, respectively.

To use this relation properly one must get accurate values of σ_o which are usually determined from stress and strain transient experiments but considerable controversy exists over the interpretation.

McLean has recently shown how to deduce σ_o accurately from stress drop experiments, as a function of temperature and directional solidification for the $\gamma\text{-}\gamma^1 \text{Cr}_3\text{C}_2$ in situ composites and for the $\gamma\text{-}\gamma^1$ matrix alloy. The values of σ_o so obtained are identical with the flow stress at creep strain rates and are the sum of the effects of the barriers to dislocation motion through the matrix, by climb around γ^1 particles, and the Orowan bowing between carbide fibres. It turns out that the friction stress and kinetics of deformation of the composite are determined by the matrix behaviour, whereas its creep strength depends on the distribution of the stress between fibre and matrix. The exponent in equation (16) turns out to be about 4 and the activation energy of $325 \pm 20 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

However there are difficulties which remain unresolved. Orowan bowing is not expected to be very temperature dependent and if the friction stress is controlled by Orowan bowing it should increase with decrease of fibre spacing. The opposite is observed. McLean explains this as being due to a layer of γ^1 precipitate formed upon the fibres which decreases the amount of γ^1 available to harden the matrix; the amount of γ^1 in the matrix will decrease with decreasing fibre diameter. Such coats are observed.

8. FATIGUE

The lack of a general theory of fatigue in conventional constructional materials (metals) makes the derivation of general rules governing fatigue of composites difficult, even for unidirectional stressing. Since many resin-based composites are poor conductors of heat an additional complication arises due to internal heating. Generally rates of application of an oscillating stress should be kept below 20 Hz if heating effects are to be avoided and "pure" fatigue behaviour observed. The extreme anisotropy of the strength also means that for an unidirectional laminate a small departure from uni-axial stressing can produce a large change in fatigue life (Hashin and Rotem, 23).

Four types of damage are identified in composite laminates with a resin matrix. These are (a) fibre breakage at stresses exceeding the strength of the weakest fibre in the composite. This is followed by debonding of the fibre from the surrounding matrix and usually by cracking of the matrix. The specimen may then

become useless due to progressive debonding of fibre and matrix. If debonding does not occur rather little fatigue tends to be observed in specimens stressed parallel to the fibres.

The fatigue mechanism in the matrix itself is similar to that in metals in the sense that crack initiation and crack propagation normal to an applied tensile stress is the way in which failure takes place. A crack propagating in the matrix often leads to interfacial shear failure when it strikes an interface. This means that there are two additional processes (b) matrix cracking and (c) interfacial shear failure. The fourth type of failure observed, and the one generally occurring at the lowest strain, is (d) interfacial debonding.

Except in the case of well aligned unidirectional specimens tested parallel to the fibres, all four mechanisms of damage may occur. Recently Talreja (24) has brought about a systematization of many results by assuming very plausibly, it seems to me, that the one or perhaps two (usually mechanisms (b) and (c), together if there are two) will be predominant in a limited range of applied maximum strain. Following this assumption, the fatigue life curve will consist of different parts corresponding to a different mechanism predominating. Strain, instead of stress, is chosen as the variable as both fibres and matrix are usually subject to the same strain. In some cases the fatigue limit of the matrix (ϵ_m) is replaced by the strain for transverse fibre debonding (ϵ_{db}) and this always appears to be the case if there are fibres at 90° to the applied stress.

At high stresses (strain) and low values of fatigue life (N) fibre breakage occurs and if in an unidirectional composite ϵ_m is greater than the failure strain of the fibres (ϵ_f), which is necessarily also the failure strain of the composite, (ϵ_c) then no fatigue process, in the sense of the propagation of a growing crack, occurs. This can be true for Type I graphite in epoxy, loaded parallel to the fibres.

If Talreja is correct the systematization is produced by emphasizing the strain range in the fatigue test and so, as he points out, a proper definition of the fatigue ratio is the ratio of the fatigue limit in terms of strain to the static composite fracture strain. In specimens containing fibres transverse to a tensile stress the fatigue limiting strain is the interfacial debonding strain $\epsilon_{d,b}$. If this is not the case it is the lower of ϵ_m and ϵ_c and only in the very special case referred to for Type I graphite fibres in epoxy is $\epsilon_m > \epsilon_c$; so the fatigue limiting strain will then be ϵ_c . $\epsilon_{d,b}$ can be very low indeed e.g. 0.1% in glass-epoxy and 0.4% in graphite epoxy depending on both resin and fibre type.

While producing a very useful systematization Talreja's scheme of emphasizing the strain range as the controlling variable does not by itself of course enable one to predict what the values of the fatigue life are.

Glass fibre is subject to static fatigue but oscillating stress effects are small (Aveston Kelly and Sillwood, 25). When polyester impregnated E glass strands are tested under slow cycle (0.1 Hz) fatigue conditions the time to failure is similar to that under static load.

Recent experimental results obtained at the NPL on g.r.p. indicate that in chopped strand mat there is a very much more marked fatigue effect than in the unidirectional composites and that the specimens show extensive cracking due presumably to interfacial debonding. $0^\circ/90^\circ$ cross ply specimens also show a fatigue effect at long times and this again is accompanied by debonding in the 90° plies. This is consistent with Talreja's scheme.

In specimens containing aligned glass fibres, tests are run often to 10^6 cycles at frequencies of no more than a few per second so that the times involved are considerable, usually several months. The stressed are also considerable; sufficient to produce strains of at least a few tenths of a percent. Under these conditions a considerable fraction of the life is therefore accounted for simply by static fatigue effects. Compare for example the times to failure involved in the experiments of Dharan (26) in oscillating stress fatigue and Aveston Kelly and

Sillwood in "static fatigue" of unidirectional glass-epoxy composites. The times are very similar. Aveston Kelly and Sillwood's results are well explained by slow crack growth.

While there is no doubt that there is a somewhat greater loss of strength in a given time under cyclic stressing than under static stress, nonetheless the degradation of strength due to the static stress is very important, is well understood and should be taken into account.

REFERENCES

- 1 Murthy,V.M., Bhowick,A.K. and De,S.K., "Electron Microscopy Studies of Failure Surfaces of Short Glass Fibre Rubber Composites", *J Mater Sci* 17 (1982) 709-716
- 2 Seth,R.S. and Page, D.H., "The Stress-strain curve of paper", Paper 51 in *The Role of Fundamental Research in Paper Making*, 7th Fundamental Research Symposium, British Paper and Board Industry Federation, pp 1-25
- 3 Shulgasser,K., "On the in-plane elastic constants of paper"; *Fibre Sci and Tech* 15 (1981) 257-270
- 4 Page,D.H., El Hosseiny,F., Winkler,K. and Lancaster,A.P.S.; "Elastic Modulus of Single Wood Pulp Fibres"; *J Tech Assoc Pulp and Paper Industry (TAPPI)* 60 (1977) 114-117
- 5 Kelly,A.; *Strong Solids*, 2nd Edition, Oxford University Press (1973)
- 6 Nicholls,R.; "Rigid Foams", Chapter 10 of *Composite Construction Materials Handbook*, Prentice Hall Inc (1976) pp353-372
- 7 Patel,M.R. and Finnie,I.; "Structural Features and Mechanical Properties of Rigid Cellular Plastics", *Jour of Materials*, 5 (1970), 909-932
- 8 Abd El Sayed,F.K., Jones,R. and Burgess,I.W.; "A Theoretical Approach to the deformation of Honeycomb Based Composite Materials Composites", *Composites*, 10 (1979) 209-214
- 9 Cunningham,A.; "Modulus Anisotropy of low-density cellular plastics: an aggregate model"; *Polymer*, 22 (1981) 882-885
- 10 Gibson,L.J., Easterling,K.E. and Ashby,M.F.; "The Structure and Mechanics of Cork", *Proc R Soc Lond A* 377 (1981) 99-117 and see references therein as well as forthcoming papers in *Proc R Soc Lond*
- 11 Hashin,Z. and Shtrikman,S.; "A variational approach to the theory of the elastic behaviour of multiphase materials"; *J Mech Phys Solids*, 11 (1963) 127-140
- 12 Lee,H.C. and Gurland,J.; "Hardness and deformation of cemented tungsten carbide", *Mat Sci and Eng*, 33 (1978) 125-133
- 13 Murray,M.J.; "Fracture of Tungsten Carbide Cobalt Alloys: an example of spatially constrained crack tip opening displacement"; *Proc R Soc Lond A* 356 (1977) 483-508
- 14 Mileiko,S.T.; "The Tensile Strength and Ductility of Continuous Fibre Composites", *J Mater Sci*, 4 (1969) 974-977
- 15 Garmon,G. and Thompson,R.B.; "A Theory for the Mechanical Properties of Metal Matrix Composites at Ultimate Loading", *Met Trans* 4 (1973) 863-873
- 16 Harlow,D.G. and Phoenix,S.L.; "Probability Distributions for the Strength of Composite Materials II. A convergent sequence for tight bounds"; *Int J Fract* 17 (1981) 601-630
- 17 Batdorf,S.B. and Ghaffarian,R.; "Statistical Treatment of Stress Concentration Factors in Damaged Composites". *J Mater Sci Letters* in press (1982)
- 18 Kelly,A. and Lilholt,H.; "Stress Strain Curve of a Fibre Reinforced Composite", *Phil Mag* 20 (1969) 311-328
- 19 Brown,L.M. and Clarke,D.R.; "The work hardening of fibrous composites with special reference to the copper-tungsten system"; *Act Met* 25 (1977) 563-570
- 20 McLean,M.; "Directional Solidification of High Temperature Alloys", *The Metals Society*, London, in press (1982)
- 21 McDanel,D., Signorelli,R.A. and Weeton, J.W.; NASA Report No TND-4173 (1967)
- 22 Street,K.N.; "Creep Behaviour of Fibre Composite Materials", PhD Thesis, London (1971)
- 23 Hashin,Z. and Rotem,A.; "A fatigue failure criterion for fiber reinforced materials"; *J Comp Mat* 7 (1973) 448-464
- 24 Talreja,R.; "Fatigue of Composite Materials: damage mechanisms and fatigue-life diagrams"; *Proc R Soc Lond A* 378 (1981) 461-475

25 Aveston, J., Kelly, A. and Sillwood, J.; "Long Term Strength of Glass Reinforced Plastics in wet environments"; in Advances in Composite Materials, 3rd International Conference on Composite Materials, Paris, France. Edited by A.R. Bunsell et al, Pergamon Press (1980) 556-568

26 Dharan, C.K.H.; "Fatigue failure in graphite fibre and glass fibre polymer composites"; J Mater Sci 10 (1975) 1665-1670

TABLES

TABLE 1

PROPERTY		GENERAL 2-DIMENSIONAL HEXAGONAL STRUCTURE	REGULAR HEXAGONAL STRUCTURE
LINEAR ELASTIC PROPERTIES	E_1	$E_s \frac{t^3}{l^3} \frac{\cos \theta}{(h/l + \sin \theta) \sin^2 \theta}$	$\frac{4}{\sqrt{3}} E_s \frac{t^3}{l^3} = \frac{2}{3} E_s \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_s}\right)^3$
	E_2	$E_s \frac{t^3}{l^3} \frac{(h/l + \sin \theta)}{\cos^3 \theta}$	
	ν_1	$\frac{\cos^2 \theta}{(h/l + \sin \theta) \sin \theta}$	
	ν_2	$\frac{(h/l + \sin \theta) \sin \theta}{\cos^2 \theta}$	
	G	$E_s \frac{t^3}{l^3} \frac{(h/l + \sin \theta)}{(h/l)^2 (2h/l + 1) \cos \theta}$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} E_s \frac{t^3}{l^3} = \frac{3}{8} E_s \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_s}\right)^3$
ELASTIC BUCKLING	$\dagger \sigma_{el}$	$E_s \frac{t^3}{l^3} \frac{(\beta^*)^2}{6 (h/l)^2 \cos \theta}$	$0.22 E_s \frac{t^3}{l^3} = 0.14 E_s \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_s}\right)^3$
PLASTIC COLLAPSE	$(\sigma_1)_{pl}$	$\sigma_y \frac{t^2}{l^2} \frac{1}{2 (h/l + \sin \theta) \sin \theta}$	$\frac{2}{3} \frac{t^2}{l^2} \sigma_y = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_y \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_s}\right)^2$
	$(\sigma_2)_{pl}$	$\sigma_y \frac{t^2}{l^2} \frac{1}{2 \cos^2 \theta}$	

$$\frac{\rho}{\rho_s} = \frac{t}{l} \frac{(h/l + 2)}{2 \cos \theta (h/l + \sin \theta)} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \frac{t}{l} \text{ for regular hexagons}$$

$\dagger \beta$ is a constant equal to about $\pi/3$ for $1 \geq (h/l) \geq 2$

TABLE 2 (units MPa)

	Calculated	Measured
$E_1 E_2$	15	13 \pm 5
G	4	4.3 \pm 1.5
ν	1.0	0.5 \pm 0.05
Elastic collapse stress	1.5	0.7 \pm 0.2

Young's modulus and density of cork cell wall material are found to be 9 GN/m^2 and 1150 kg/m^3 respectively

Fig 1 Stress=strain curve of paper replotted in S.I. units, from R S Seth and D H Page from PPR 316 of the Pulp and Paper Research Institute of Canada

Fig 2 Stress strain curve of holocellulose fibres replotted in S.I. units. The fibres had been kinked prior to these tensile curves.

Fig 3 Calculated dependence of steady state creep rate on stress for a composite from an assumed dependence on stress of the creep rate for matrix and fibres (from ref 22) $m = n_2$ in this paper and $n = n_1$ - subscript f refers to fibres

Fig 4 Composite stress sensitivity calculated from Fig 3 (from ref 22) $m = n_2$ in this paper and $n = n_1$ - subscript f refers to fibres